

Report

Applying *Isodata* and *K-means* algorithms of Unsupervised Classification methods of ENVI for Airborne CASI Image Processing; University of Southampton

This paper focuses on the technical aspects of the using the imaging spectrometry for monitoring the coastal and hydrological environment of the Test River (southern England, UK). In this case study it is impossible using usual satellite images due to the extremely shallow and clear waters. The hydrological characteristics of the river (its clearness and shallowness) make it very difficult to use visible region bands for a good results, due to wavelength-dependence of absorption clear water absorbs more wavelengths in the red spectrum than the blue region (Acornley *et al*, 2008). Besides, shallowness of the river bed makes the absorption by the water in the visible region not sufficient to measure changes of value with water depth. And finally, the narrowness of the river causes some difficulties as well: in the period of the algae blooming river can be blocked up by the weeds.

It is therefore necessary to use an airborne sensor, as it meets the requirements of high spatial resolution, flexibility of timing data, and surveying the linear geomorphologic forms of river channels (Milton, 2009). For the estimation of shallow water properties and habitats we used the techniques for combining the information in various spectral bands to produce a depth-invariant index of the bottom type (Lyzenga, 1981).

Fig.1. Initial image, geometrically wrong

During the practical we used the geometrically-corrected airborne image CASI-2 data, collected during the NCAVEO 2006 which has good sensitivity of the NIR band to detect every nuance of water depth' changing of several centimetres (Milton, 2009). Besides, we used ground data as an Excel-table spreadsheet Rtest_survey2006.xls containing information about water depth, substrate type, and vegetation. Ground data with gravel as a substrate were collected by the Dr. Sear team.

Fig.2. Main colour composite of RTest_C2006_atm.hdr

Firstly, we tried the RTest_C1994 (Fig.1), but it did not meet the requirements of geometrical correctness when comparing it visually with OS Map and we used Rtest_C2006_atm.hdr (Fig.2).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	MapX	MapY	Depth(cm)	Substrate type	822nm	709nm	542nm	log22	log100	log542	
2	438560	140318	66	Gravel	546	273	263	6.362	5.669	5.572	
3	438579	140318	61	Gravel	440	255	250	6.086	5.541	5.552	
4	438578	140318	59	Gravel	444	279	297	6.095	5.631	5.693	
5	438577	140318	43	Gravel	521	341	375	6.255	5.931	5.926	
6	438576	140318	13	Gravel	718	462	450	6.576	6.113	6.108	
7	438574	140319	9	Gravel	1693	990	747	7.428	6.956	6.616	
8	438573	140319	9	Gravel	1686	916	701	7.436	6.82	6.552	
9	438571	140320	14	Gravel	1256	747	637	7.125	6.616	6.496	
10	438570	140320	17	Gravel	869	534	489	6.767	6.28	6.192	
11	438569	140320	15	Gravel	729	445	423	6.591	6.088	6.047	
12	438568	140321	6	Gravel	1018	603	521	6.925	6.401	6.265	
13	438566	140321	7	Gravel	1315	746	587	7.181	6.614	6.376	
14	438566	140321	15	Gravel	991	621	542	6.898	6.431	6.265	
15	438564	140321	34	Gravel	722	442	422	6.562	6.091	6.045	
16	438563	140322	26	Gravel	665	463	461	6.529	6.137	6.133	
17	438562	140322	31	Gravel	651	411	408	6.478	6.018	6.011	

Fig.3. Rtest_survey2006.xls Table containing Ground data, and calculated logarithms

At the next step the new images were created by using the *Band Math* tool of ENVI. The aim of this was to have a look at the relationship of water depth and natural logarithm of reflectance. Three bands were used: 826nm, 703nm and 544nm for creating the

images, respectively log825, log544 and log544. While logarithms from 826nm and 703nm were similar in relationship water depth-DN, the log544 had distinctive relationship; therefore, we used the pair of images calculated from log544nm and log703nm as our two main base images for the research.

Fig.4. Scatter plot of relationship between water-depth and log703 of the reflectance

ig.5. Scatter plot of relationship between water-depth and log544 of the reflectance

Fig.6. Scatter plot of relationship between water-depth and log826 of the reflectance

The results of the relationship between the bottom depth and the logarithm of reflectance can be easily seen (Fig.4-6), there is “linear relationship between water depth and the logarithm of reflectance after the effect of the atmosphere has been removed” (Acornley et al, 1995).

At the next working step we loaded the point collection from the ground data measurements (file Transect.txt) and created a ROI (Region Of Interest) from given points (Fig.7). A sample of this point collection with known depth was necessary to research the relationship between depth and the log of reflectance at 826 nm. Then we applied this relationship to the rest of the river channel (Acornley et al, 1995). For the calculations of the logarithms the values of digital numbers were collected using Cursor Location Value tool of ENVI.

Fig.7. ROI points of interest (loaded from file Transect1.txt)

Then we calculated the coefficient k_{544}/k_{703} using the Excel. This coefficient is necessary constant value which we use for calculating the new image from the existing log544 and log703, as using the proposed formula (Milton 2009, p.28) we can obtain the value of the DN in new image, free from dependence of water depth. For the k_{544}/k_{703} calculation we received firstly variance (spread) and then the covariance (joint relationship) between the two spectral bands - 544dn and 703dn respectively (Milton 2009). After calculations we received the final value of the coefficient k_{544}/k_{703} equal to 0.644705. For our research enough to accept $k_{544}/k_{703}=0.64$ (Fig.8).

Fig.8. Using Excel table for calculation of the k544/k703 coefficient

Using the k_{544}/k_{703} coefficient and two previously obtained images (log703 and log544), we then easily created new depth-invariant image, DI-544-703.hdr. In new image we restore the ROI file RTest_C2006.roi, after which our new depth-

Fig.9 Depth-invariant DI-544-703 Image (right) received using k544/k703 calculation

Fig.10. Creation of mask (water area) using ROI tools in ENVI

invariant image show a blue polygon line (Fig.9).

Having created the mask from the “river-area”, we apply unsupervised classification, consisting of 3 classes, to the new DI-544-703 image, using the mask to exclude all other regions we do not interested in: non-water areas. Different regions in water are coloured in a contrast way (Fig.10).

Fig.11. Final Map of the River Test habitat made using ENVI software

We tried both *Isodata* and *K-means* algorithms of unsupervised classification with the following results: while using the *Isodata* we found out that the result of classes is better at splitting the area into four and five classes: the areas are become more refined and look visually better. While splitting into three classes the *K-means* algorithm is also suitable enough, and it makes the classes more uniform and homogeneous within the single class. However, both algorithms are using the iteration process of classifying pixels into the suitable cluster, and in principle, both algorithms can be used for the classification.

Finally, we overlay the original image in grey scale by the new-created classified image of river Task to show representatively picture of surroundings and classified image (Fig.11).

We tried classification using four and five classes as well, which, however, make the image more detailed and therefore, less representative and visual, so that three classes are optimal in this case.

Finally cartographic grid and map layout were added for new thematic map from the image showing different regions within water area. Using this map we can clearly distinguish different-coloured regions with in-stream habitats in water of the Test River (Fig.11).

To conclude, we can summarise that airborne imaging spectrometry has a very good effect in investigating the river channel habitats in the shallow and clear waters where usual satellite imagery are ineffective. As it is justly reported (Acornley *et al*, 1995), airborne spectrometry has great potential as an excellent tool for estimating water depth and environment in shallow rivers.

References:

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